

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Dlx4.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Dlx4 as a candidate
9 gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Wu, D., Mandal, S., Choi, A., Anderson, A., Prochazkova, M., Perry, H., Gil-Da-Silva-Lopes, V.L.,
12 Lao, R., Wan, E., Tang, P.L.F. and Kwok, P.Y., 2015. DLX4 is associated with orofacial clefting and
13 abnormal jaw development. Human molecular genetics, 24(15), pp.4340-4352.